

Comparisons of material characteristics for implementation in mammographic phantoms

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Abstract— The following work presents the development of structures and techniques for implementation in mammographic phantoms focusing on the replication of anatomical and radiological characteristics of the human breast. Three-dimensional modeling was performed in the software *Blender* and *Fusion360*. During the process, four different experimental structures were developed and tested, each composed of three distinct parts, the outer structure, filling and internal structures, in order to evaluate the selection of compounds and density variation, seeking the best combination for anatomical fidelity and radiological response. The research also discusses different 3D printing methods and parameters and how those factors affect the phantom's geometric accuracy and physical properties. The results demonstrated that PLA-based structures ensured greater dimensional accuracy and contrast in radiographic images, while TPU-based structures presented better mechanical adaptability, although requiring more attention to the printing parameters to minimize artifacts. With respect to fillers, beeswax presented the best performance with less variation in pixel values, greater homogeneity and also was more manageable due to its thermoplastic behavior than the paraffin gel.

Keywords — 3D printing; Breast phantom; Image quality; Mammography; Materials studies

I. INTRODUCTION

In the field of mammography, phantoms or breast simulator objects play a crucial role in assessing image quality and equipment calibration. These devices are specially designed to replicate the density, composition, and radiation interaction with human tissue [1]. By accurately simulating the characteristics of breast tissue, phantoms are essential for testing and optimizing mammography systems, ensuring the acquisition of reliable images [2].

The versatility of phantoms allows the simulation of a variety of acquisition techniques, enabling the testing and optimization of mammography systems as well as image processing techniques. This not only ensures the safety of examinations but also the quality of the produced images [3]. However, a significant challenge associated with these devices is their high acquisition cost, which may hinder the adoption of best practices and the replication of studies involving quality metrics and image processing [4].

Printing 3D breast phantoms or specific structures with PLA or TPU offers several advantages, including reduced cost, ease of reproduction, and customization possibilities according to the specific needs of the study or professional training [5]. Furthermore, the ability to accurately simulate the characteristics of human breast tissue allows for comprehensive testing to ensure the quality of mammographic images and optimize image processing techniques.

3D printing technologies have emerged as a promising tool for creating breast phantoms, offering advantages such as cost reduction, customization, and reproducibility. However, the choice of materials, ranging from rigid polymers like PLA (polylactic acid) to flexible TPU (thermoplastic polyurethane), and soft fillers like beeswax and gel paraffin directly impacts their ability to mimic human breast tissue properties in mammography simulations.

PLA is a biodegradable polymer derived from renewable sources, such as corn starch or sugarcane [6], and its popularity in 3D printing is due to its favorable properties, such as low melting point and good layer adhesion. The relatively low melting temperature of PLA, compared to other materials used in 3D printing [7], makes it suitable for medical applications, such as modeling breast simulator objects, as it reduces the risk of deformations during the printing process.

The TPU class of polymers is used in various applications as a result of their exceptional mechanical properties and flexibility. This material is mainly composed of soft compounds, such as polyol, and hard compounds, isocyanates. The proportion of these materials determines the malleability, softness, and strength. It exhibits excellent tensile strength, tear resistance, and good elasticity, making it ideal for applications that require both flexibility and durability [8, 9].

Observing the results presented in the work of Pinheiro et. al. [10], it can be seen that PLA and TPU demonstrated significant proximity in mass attenuation coefficient between them and to the tissues of the human breast. Printing 3D breast phantoms or specific structures with PLA or TPU offers several advantages, including reduced cost, ease of reproduction, and customization possibilities according to the

specific needs of the study or professional training [5].

To better simulate the density and texture properties of human breast tissue beeswax and gel paraffin have been explored. Beeswax, a natural material produced by honeybees, exhibits favorable thermoplastic properties, including low thermal conductivity and a melting range between 62°C and 64°C [11]. Gel paraffin, on the other hand, is a synthetic material widely used in medical applications due to its thermal stability and adjustable radiological properties. Composed primarily of saturated hydrocarbons, its density (0.9 g/cm³) and low hardness make it suitable for mimicking soft tissues [12].

Through comparative analyses of image quality parameters, this work aims to identify which material combination performs best in terms of tissue representativeness and structural stability for developing a low-cost, highly configurable anthropomorphic mammographic phantom with simple replication process. This has potential applications in equipment quality control, system calibration, and validation of new image processing algorithms in breast diagnostics.

II. METHODS

A. 3D Modeling

The modeling process was performed using *Fusion360* and *Blender* software, utilizing the best sets of techniques and tools that each offers for the specific needs of the project.

Fusion360 was used, due to its excellent performance in developing symmetrical projects with low geometric complexity [13], for creating the external structures that simultaneously act as simulators of the skin layer of the breast and as physical containment for the internal set of structures and filling. A rectangular structure of 125mm × 32mm × 16mm was designed, composed of 4 identical internal compartments of 30mm × 30mm × 15mm surrounded by 1mm of material on the sides and bottom, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. 3D Model of individual external structure

The development of internal structures was performed in *Blender* using the *GeometryNodes* tool. The programming logic shown in Figure 2 was applied to develop a

customizable and randomizable organic body capable of simulating different arrangements and densities of human breast fibroglandular tissue.

Fig. 2. Programming logic fluxogram

The main components of the filling pattern composition are the adjustable *Noise* and *Voronoi* textures, in addition to the *Color Ramp* with linear RGB pattern adjusted to Pos 0.135.

From variations in the *Threshold* parameters in *Volume Mesh* and *Scale* in *Noise Texture*, four Regions of Interest (ROI) were selected with different manifestations of the created base model, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Example of internal structure

B. Printing and assembling

The manufacturing process began with the printing of four external structures (two in PLA and two in TPU), plus four sets of four diferernt internal structures (ROIs), equally divided between PLA and TPU, totaling sixteen internal components. Slicing and print settings were performed using *UltiMaker Cura* with the following parameters:

- PLA: Nozzle temperature 200°C, bed temperature 60°C, speed 60 mm/s, 90% infill, and tree supports

- TPU: Nozzle temperature 210°C, bed temperature 60°C, speed 50 mm/s, 90% infill, and tree supports

Each external structure received a set of four ROIs of the same material as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Printed set (PLA)

For the filling materials:

- Beeswax was melted in a water bath at 70°C for approximately 35 minutes with constant stirring to eliminate bubbles
- Gel paraffin was heated to 90°C in a metal container over flame until reaching uniform viscosity

The final arrangement is as follows:

- PC structure (PLA): Filled with beeswax and cooled to room temperature
- PG structure (PLA): Filled with gel paraffin and cooled to room temperature
- TC structure (TPU): Filled with beeswax and cooled to room temperature
- TG structure (TPU): Filled with gel paraffin and cooled to room temperature

C. Image acquisition and testing

For the quantitative tests, the structures were taken to a Siemens Mammomat Fusion model mammography machine at a private hospital in Uberlândia, where acquisitions were performed following the hospital's standard protocols, resulting in the image shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Mammography acquisition result of the 16 ROIs

The testing phase was then initiated in *MatLab*, where for each of the 16 regions of interest, the metrics of mean, standard deviation and variance were calculated.

The following mathematical formulas were used to calculate the metrics for each of the 16 regions of interest in *MatLab*:

$$\text{Mean}(\mu) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Standard Deviation}(\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Variance}(\sigma^2) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2 \quad (3)$$

Where:

- N is the number of pixels in the ROI
- x_i is the pixel value at position i
- μ is the mean pixel value

III. RESULTS

After the printing and assembly processes, the structure shown in Figure 5 was the final result. Regarding the printing process, it is particularly noteworthy that the PLA showed no deformations, while the TPU-based structures displayed minor printing artifacts (visible as texture irregularities in the acquired images), which may possibly be addressed through optimized 3D printing parameters such as increased extrusion temperature (220-230°C), reduced printing speed (30-40 mm/s), if necessary the use of specialized flexible filament print surface or the use of a more advanced 3D printer.

Fig. 6. Final arrangement

Following the extraction of the aforementioned values, Table 1 was compiled.

TABLE 1. ROI Performance by Configuration: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Variance

ROI 1	Mean	Std Dev.	Variance
CP1	88.77	50.41	2540.67
CT1	90.61	41.42	1715.86
GP1	88.08	57.74	3333.53
GT1	66.44	40.93	1674.89
ROI 2	Mean	Std Dev.	Variance
CP2	89.68	50.84	2584.43
CT2	75.35	40.55	1644.28
GP2	74.65	65.18	4248.78
GT2	56.84	40.44	1635.31
ROI 3	Mean	Std Dev.	Variance
CP3	95.51	51.58	2660.22
CT3	81.55	40.43	1634.20
GP3	89.70	61.54	3787.55
GT3	67.79	34.88	1216.27
ROI 4	Mean	Std Dev.	Variance
CP4	128.62	59.30	3516.11
CT4	102.29	64.85	4205.83
GP4	128.13	73.44	5392.87
GT4	99.71	52.82	2789.51

The radiographic performance analysis shows clear differences between the material combinations. PLA-based structures filled with paraffin gel (GP4) and beeswax (CP4) presented higher averages, with GP4 being the largest standard deviation, suggesting greater contrast than the other ROI4, in agreement with visual analysis (Fig. 5).

The combinations of ROI4 resulted in an average STD of 62,60. This can be due to the small irregularity of the shape and for being more compact (Fig.4), which produces final objects with little volume of filling materials (gel paraffin and beeswax) leaving the radiographic image of the objects with larger areas referring to the printed object.

In a qualitative evaluation of the ROIs (Fig. 4) for different printing materials, such as TPU and PLA, a greater contrast is noticeable in the ROIs of the PLA objects. This observation agrees with the quantitative data regarding the standard deviation in relation to the mean gray levels of the ROIs with PLA printing (Fig. 7A). When the ROIs with different filling materials (beeswax and paraffin) were quantitatively evaluated, similar behavior was observed for ROIs 3 and 4, showing a greater standard deviation for the ROIs filled with beeswax (Fig. 7B). Visually, however, it is not possible to clearly assess the difference in contrast between the different filling materials

Fig. 7. (A) average pixel and STD values of each ROI per type of print material; (B) average pixel and STD values of each ROI per type of fill material

For a more detailed analysis, the variation coefficient was calculated to assess the relative dispersion of the data. These measurements allow for a clearer analysis of the variations between the different printing materials (TPU and PLA) and fillers (beeswax and paraffin), as shown in the graph in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Graph of the coefficients of variation of filling materials presented in bars and the variances of filling materials represented in rows

A lower variation coefficient indicates greater data homogeneity, as the standard deviation is small relative to the mean. Based on this, the average grayscale data of the ROIs shows that the TPU objects ROIs are more heterogeneous than the PLA objects ROIs, with the exception of ROI 4. In the analysis of infill materials, the variation coefficients for beeswax ROIs are generally higher, though they exhibit similar behavior to paraffin in ROI 4 (Fig. 8). An analysis of the graph in Figure 8 shows that the variance, a measure of absolute dispersion, is lower for the ROIs filled with beeswax, indicating greater measurement stability between ROIs 1 and 3.

Calculating the coefficient of variation to wax presents higher values, which implies a greater dispersion, and can be statistically interpreted as more heterogeneous

IV. CONCLUSION

This study was successful in developing and evaluating 3D printing techniques and structures for breast phantoms using combinations of PLA/TPU structures with beeswax/gel paraffin fillers.

The TPU shell presents particularly promising characteristics for the manufacture of mammographic phantoms. Despite the challenges observed in the printing process, such as the occurrence of surface artifacts and the need for adjustments to the print parameters, its ability to maintain structural integrity after contact with beeswax and liquid gel paraffin makes it a superior option in terms of durability and dimensional consistency.

In terms of internal structures, both PLA and TPU have distinct advantages and limitations. PLA offers greater rigidity and dimensional accuracy, making it ideal for the reproduction of complex anatomical structures. However, its lower resistance to heat during filling can lead to subtle deformations. The TPU, although less rigid, shows better adaptation to thermal variations, preserving better the internal

geometry designed.

Regarding the filling materials, beeswax was a standout choice, exhibiting the lowest variance in pixel values during the quantitative analysis, which indicates lower absolute dispersion. Visually, it also demonstrated greater homogeneity, even though its coefficients of variation indicated greater relative dispersion. Additionally, beeswax is easier to handle than paraffin gel due to its lower melting point. Its thermoplastic properties facilitate the filling process, reducing the formation of bubbles and inconsistencies.

Despite technical challenges, all sample configurations maintained sufficient structural integrity for imaging tests, demonstrating the viability of this approach for cost-effective, customizable mammography phantoms. Future works should focus on refining the printing process for TPU structures and incorporating the technology and results in a complete phantom.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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